

Variables:

- **Workload (n):** The number of instances that the user needs. Elastic services allow extra instances for sudden increases in the service usage (these situations are known as peaks). The number of instances used during peaks and the duration of the peak will influence the price.
- **Instance family (fam):** This property determines the base price of an instance. Each provider has their own instance families, making the integration of all three models more challenging.
- **Region (reg):** Each instance belongs to a region. Different regions apply certain multipliers to the overall price.
- **Operating System (os):** Microsoft Azure and Amazon EC2 account for the instance's OS when estimating the price, but Google Cloud's App Engine does not. Apply a multiplier to the total price.
- **Instance type (typ):** This property is available for Amazon EC2 and Microsoft App Service. Instances may be shared instances, dedicated instances, or dedicated hosts, which can vary their cost. Apply a multiplier to the formula.
- **Memory (m):** Measured in gigabytes. It plays a role in the pricing for all providers.
- **CPU ($cpughz$ or $cpun$):** Google Cloud's Standard Environment measures the processing capacity in GHz, while Amazon, Microsoft and Google's Flexible Environment measure it in number of cores. $cpughz$ represents the number of GHz of the machine's processor, and $cpun$ is the number of cores.
- **Storage memory ($storage$):** The price of the Microsoft App Service instance can change depending on the amount of storage offered, when applying a multiplication.

Formulas:

- **Amazon EC2 formula**

$$price = n \times fam \times reg \times os \times typ \times m$$

- **Google App Engine Standard Environment formula**

$$price = n \times fam \times reg \times (m + cpughz)$$

- **Google App Engine Flexible Environment formula**

$$price = \frac{n \times reg \times (m \times c2 + cpun \times c3 + storage \times c4)}{730}$$

- **Microsoft App Service formula**

$$price = n \times fam \times reg \times os \times (m + cpun)$$

The service consumer may expect a varying workload, allowing them to flexibilise their costs based on the expected traffic. Amazon EC2 allows for this varying workload. In the formula, this is defined as the highest instances ($peakn$), and the additional instances are expected to work a set of hours per month ($peakDuration$).

- **Amazon EC2 formula if there are peak instances**

$$price = \left((n + 0.75) + \left((peakn - c1) \times \left(\left(\frac{peakDuration}{30} \right) + 0.05 \right) \right) \right) \times AmazonEC2formula$$

Some numbers are constants that are extracted using web scraping and are marked as cX . They generally refer to the price of something; for example, $c3$ in the Google Cloud Flexible formula refers to the price of each core offered by the Google Cloud service. Finally, some formulae use the number 730 because that is the number of hours in a month, and the model standardises its output as the price per hour.